

Correction

Correction: Casula, G.A. A Design Rule to Reduce the Human Body Effect on Wearable PIFA Antennas. *Electronics* 2019, 8, 244

Giovanni Andrea Casula *

Dipartimento di Ingegneria Elettrica ed Elettronica, Università di Cagliari, Piazza D'Armi, 09123 Cagliari, Italy; giorgio.montisci@unica.it

* Correspondence: a.casula@diee.unica.it; Tel.: +39-070-675-5787

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In the original version of this article [1], the author forgot to insert a co-author. The author apologizes for the original error. To correct this oversight, Giorgio Montisci has been added as an author, and the Author Contributions have been corrected.

The corrected author list and author contributions are provided below:

Author List and Affiliations:

Giovanni Andrea Casula* and Giorgio Montisci

Dipartimento di Ingegneria Elettrica ed Elettronica, Università di Cagliari, Piazza D'Armi, 09123 Cagliari, Italy; giorgio.montisci@unica.it

* Correspondence: a.casula@diee.unica.it; Tel.: +39-070-675-5787

Author Contributions: The main contribution to the work has been made by G.A.C., but the contribution of the co-author G.M. has been essential during the review preparation of the article, where substantial modifications and integrations have been made within a very close deadline. Moreover, also in the preliminary phase, the suggestions of G.M. helped the author to investigate the problem and to select the most important numerical tests for the structures to investigate. In particular, G.M. contributed to the Investigation, Writing-Review & Editing, and to Funding Acquisition.

References

1. Casula, G.A. A Design Rule to Reduce the Human Body Effect on Wearable PIFA Antennas. *Electronics* **2019**, *8*, 244. [[CrossRef](#)]

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